

The Constitution of Mollugogenol B -A New Sapogenin from *Mollugo hirta*

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The isolation of a new triterpenoid sapogenol, mollugogenol A, from *Mollugo hirta* (syn. *M. lotoides*) was reported earlier¹ from this laboratory. It has now been possible to isolate another new sapogenol, mollugogenol B, from the same plant and the present communication deals with its structure.

Mollugogenol B (Ia), $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$, m.p. 222-25°, $[\alpha]_D^{36} +91^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test and a reddish-brown colour with tetranitromethane. It formed a diacetate (Ib), $C_{34}H_{52}O_4$, m.p. 194-97°, and a dibenzoate (Ic), $C_{44}H_{56}O_4$, m.p. 222-26°. U. V. spectrum [λ_{max} 243, 251 and 261 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.17, 4.23 and 4.07)] of mollugogenol B is compatible with those of either olean-11:12, 13:18-dienes² or hop-15, 17 (21)-dienes³. That mollugogenol B is a dihydroxy hopane derivative having 15, 17 (21)-diene system was clear from its i.r. $[\nu_{max}^{nujol}]$ 3450 cm^{-1} (OH); 790 and 772 cm^{-1} (cf. i.r. spectrum of methyl leucotyldienate (III)³ prepared from leucotylic acid), n.m.r. and mass spectral studies. The n.m.r. spectrum (60 Mc; $CHCl_3$) of mollugogenol B showed signals at 0.85 (2Me, s), 0.94 (Me, d, $J=6.2$ c.p.s.), 0.97 (Me, d, $J=6.2$ c.p.s.) 0.99 (2Me, s), 1.14 (Me, s), 1.33 (Me, s) δ for eight methyl groups and an AB quartet consisting of two doublets centred at 6.21 and 5.59 δ ($J=10$ c.p.s.)^{3,4} corresponding to two adjacent olefinic protons at C-15 and C-16. Two broad signals centred at 4.1 and 3.18 δ are due to two axial protons attached to carbon bearing hydroxyl groups at C-6 and C-3. The mass spectrum of dihydromollugogenol B (IIa), $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$, m.p. 223-26° (obtained by catalytic hydrogenation of mollugogenol B over Adams' catalyst in ethanol) showed the molecular ion at m/e 442 together with peaks at m/e 424 (M-H₂O) and 399 (M-43; M-HC $\langle \begin{smallmatrix} CH_3 \\ CH_3 \end{smallmatrix} \rangle$). The peaks at m/e 223, 205 and 187 corresponding to ions (a), (a-H₂O) and (a-2H₂O) are compatible with fragmentation pattern associated with 3 β -hydroxy-4, 4-dimethyl triterpenes⁵ having an additional hydroxyl group in ring A and/or B.

Dihydromollugogenol B (IIa) gave pale yellow colour with tetranitromethane and showed a terminal absorption at 205 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.54) for a tetrasubstituted double bond. Oxidation of (IIa) with CrO_3 -pyridine complex yielded a colourless diketone (IIb), $C_{30}H_{46}O_2$, m.p. 209-12°, which gave positive Zimmermann's colour test for a β -keto group thereby

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suggesting the presence of a 3-hydroxyl group in mollugogenol B. The diketone (IIb) on Wolff-Kishner reduction furnished a monoketone (IIc), C₃₀H₄₈O, m.p. 178-80°, [ν $\frac{\text{nujol}}{\text{max}}$ 1710 cm⁻¹ (>C=O)], which did not respond to Zimmermann's colour test for 3-keto group. The ketone (IIc) was identified as zeorininone^{6,7} (IIc) by mixed m.p., t.l.c. and i.r. spectra. Mollugogenol B formed the diacetate (Ib) on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine at 0°C thus suggesting the hydroxyl groups to be equatorial. On the basis of the observations made so far, mollugogenol B may be represented as 3 β , 6 α -dihydroxy-hop-15, 17 (21)-diene (Ia).

We would like to mention that triterpenes of the hopane group have so far been found to occur in the free state and these were isolated mainly from lichens and ferns. Mollugogenol B is perhaps the first hopane derivative occurring as a glycoside in plant.

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